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Beyond the Wheels: Exploring Jeepney Drivers' Work Struggles and Navigational Behavior

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Abstract

This study unveiled the challenges faced by jeepney drivers in the Philippines, a unique form of transportation prevalent only in this country. Due to the localized nature of jeepneys, there is a lack of comparative studies with foreign vehicle transportation systems. The research aimed to explore the economic, socio-cultural, and behavioral dimensions of modern jeepney drivers and their impact on navigational practices. Utilizing purposive sampling, the study involved seven (7) jeepney drivers from Pasig City. The research analyzed their experiences, focusing on economic hardships and daily interactions with passengers. It was found that drivers' decision-making processes are heavily influenced by road conditions, which directly affect their ability to ensure passenger and personal safety. More so, the study examined the drivers' strategies for adapting to road difficulties within the framework of transport policy. The findings indicate that the work-related struggles of jeepney drivers significantly affect their navigational behavior, intersecting with socio-cultural, economic, and behavioral aspects.

Keywords: *work challenges, navigational behavior, socio-cultural, economic, behavioral aspects*

Introduction

Due to their convenience, comfort, and simplified usage, jeepneys remain an ordinary means of transportation for many commuters and play a significant part in the lives of Filipinos. According to Frisnedi et al. (2021), even with the fair fee and the earnings they make after a long and exhausting drive, their salaries are still insufficient. Additionally, jeepney drivers encounter a variety of difficulties; among these include the long hours at work and fatigue they experience in high traffic (Ranis et al., 2021). In view of this, some drivers are compelled to drive irresponsibly in traffic jams, which can worsen the condition of the road and occasionally may result in an accident. Furthermore, maintaining the general health of jeepney drivers while driving is significantly influenced by their working circumstances. Owing to the nature of their jobs, spending a lot of time confined to one place might be stressful (Seva, 2023). Furthermore, as noted by Balansag (2019), area management and construction projects frequently turn into significant obstacles, resulting in route closures and compelling jeepney drivers to take longer, alternate routes in order to avoid traffic. This can occasionally result in a standstill situation where jeepneys congest on the narrow road.

As a result, according to Renis et al. (2021), issues at work including long hours, low salary, along with worsening circumstances like traffic, cramped workspaces, and protracted road construction, could cause them stressed out and impede them from making the most of their own driving skills. Even though it's dangerous, numerous drivers still drive recklessly and violate the law. According to Webb, F. M., & Moyers (2020), "Some individuals start to believe that their actions will have no measurable consequences on the outside world." All users of the road are put at risk by this concept; thus, they must use caution and vigilance to stay clear of drivers who drive recklessly. Any flaw in the trip might have an impact not just on the commuters' life but also on the jeepney driver's overall well-being.

Nevertheless, the suggestion that navigational behavior corresponded with the drivers' work challenges was not always valid. Long working hours, low income, custom traffic, challenging job surroundings, road construction, and a lack of training have all contributed to an increase in dangerous driving among Philippine Jeepney drivers. According to Cañada et al., (2021), physical or internal abatement that redounds in fatigue could produce dropped alertness, poor judgment, and slower response times, serving as a vital factor that supported parlous driving practices. multitudinous causes, including lack of sleep, lengthy workdays, and stress, contributed to fatigue. A variety of treatments, similar as encouraging drivers to get respectable sleep, setting driving time restrictions, and offering rest breaks, could be employed to lower the trouble of accidents caused by fatigue. These difficulties could peril both the driver and the passengers, and they demanded to be addressed in order to ameliorate driving conduct. This signified the most to the drivers who were willing to take conduct ahead of their will for them to drive vehicles safely, without any possible conflict and with the agreement of the law, they would alleviate the rising cases of accidents due to reckless driving.

In spite of that, it's also vital to remember that drivers are also responsible for their feelings and conduct and that the external factors aren't solely the reasons why reckless driving happens. According to a journal composition named "Reckless Driving Law in the Philippines- What You Need to Know" published in 2023, it's driving without being conservative in controlling their vehicle. Similar to using phones while driving, talking to other people in the middle of the road and being out of focus. Recent work in the fields suggests that the challenges faced by jeepney drivers may not always affect aggressive driving. Other criteria, similar as personality or driving style, may play a larger influence when determining whether a driver is careless as there are multitudinous factors that play to impact the driver's performance together with other circumstances that enable them to completely engage in the significance of driving

and ensuring the passengers safety. Anyhow, whether they drive a jeepney or other vehicles, they should be alert when driving to avoid any accidents. (Batara, 2021). Although reckless driving is punishable by law, there are still a lot of drivers who do not consider driving as serious as it takes when accidents happen. Driving without caution makes it dangerous as they do not consider other vehicles around them, especially the safety of their own and the passengers.

It is uncertain whether a solution will be found to reduce the heavy traffic in Pasig City and other parts of the city, in addition to what has already been discussed regarding the causes of continuous traffic and invisible traffic jams on the city's streets. Although the government launched and carried out a number of projects, little to no progress was made. In order to lower the number of cars on the road, this includes the introduction of government-funded buses as well as PUJ codes and restrictions. Furthermore, not all of the government's suggested fixes have really helped drivers of older jeepney models. It is evident that the government of the Philippines has prioritized modernizing jeepney transportation. (Atos et al., 2021).

Numerous issues that jeepney drivers in the Philippines deal with have an enormous effect on how they drive. Obstacles for challenging labor include unpleasant settings, road construction, low salaries, extended working hours, and traffic congestion. Because of their lengthy working hours and insufficient salary, jeepney drivers must put daily revenue ahead of their safety. This may result in careless driving that endangers the passengers' safety. A driver's ability to drive may be further restricted by unpleasant working conditions, which may result in drivers' fatigue. To improve the driving practices of jeepney drivers in the Philippines, it is critical to address the issues they experience. This may indicate less traffic, improved working conditions, and increased training. If these changes were made, possibly everyone could use Jeeps to travel efficiently and safely. Although the focus of this study is on how jeepney drivers deal with stress that are brought by factors like fatigue and low income, future studies may take into account other external factors like safety concerns, the tools or equipment the driver uses, and other elements that might affect the driver's performance. Researchers think that more strict supervision of safe driving practices and focused regulation of the Highway Traffic Law can be established in order to protect the affordability of public transportation, especially jeepneys.

Research Questions

The objective of the study is to determine the perspective, experiences and daily work struggles of the jeepney drivers in Pasig City. It also aims to explore and understand the different factors affecting their navigational behavior, including their decision making, coping styles and strategies in the economic challenges, uncertainties while driving and policy changes, and its fundamental impact in their livelihood.

1. How do jeepney drivers in Pasig City perceive and experience their daily work struggles, including economic challenges, road conditions, and passenger interactions, and how do these perceptions influence their navigational behavior within the city?
2. What social and cultural factors shape the navigational choices and decision-making processes of jeepney drivers in Pasig City, and how do these factors intersect with their work struggles to influence their route selection and customer interactions?
3. In what ways do the work struggles and navigational behavior of jeepney drivers in Pasig City contribute to the broader socio-economic dynamics of the region, and how can a deeper understanding of these drivers' experiences inform policy initiatives and interventions to improve their working conditions and the public transportation system?

Literature Review

The Intersection of Jeepney Drivers' Socioeconomic Challenges and Navigational Behavior

Tus et al. (2021) defined jeepneys as the "king of the roads" as they are the most in-demand basic mode of transportation in the Philippines, much more accessible, affordable, and flexible. It facilitates the movement and availability of work and community resources. Jeepneys are both a means of transportation and a symbol in Filipino communities. while Batara (2021) stated that road safety is more than simply checking both directions before crossing the road. Cañada (2021) stated that lack of sleep, working at night and sleeping during the day, and inactivity create tiredness. Fatigue can result from drinking, drug usage, poor sleep, diet, and health, which affects the overall performance of jeepney drivers.

In 2020, even before the pandemic, public transport drivers' lives were challenging because their average wage barely covered food, rental fees, power, and other expenditures. Public transportation facilitates the movement and availability of work, community resources, medical care, and recreational possibilities in many areas around the Philippines. The lowest fare is advantageous for both vehicle owners and commuters (Ranis et al., 2021). The Philippines' transport system relied on jeepneys. Nevertheless, jeepney drivers are considered the poorest in the Philippines.

Numerous studies have argued that several navigational behaviors were interdependent with the drivers' work struggles, and Jeepney Drivers' were among them. The researchers aimed to examine the different facets of psychological, physiological, and environmental factors of their working experience that primed aspects of their modal behavior. This study aimed to examine the factors that corresponded to their struggles and how these factors delved into their navigational behavior. The study encompassed the aspects of the pivotal issues concurring with the struggles of the jeepney drivers and based on its effect on their patterns of navigational conduct.

However, the suggestion that navigational actions corresponded with the drivers' work challenges was not always valid. Long working

hours, low income, traffic congestion, challenging job environments, road construction, and a lack of training have all contributed to an increase in dangerous driving among Philippine Jeepney drivers. According to Cañada et al. (2021), physical or mental depletion that resulted in fatigue could cause decreased attentiveness, poor judgment, and slower reaction times, serving as a crucial factor that supported risky driving practices. Numerous causes, including lack of sleep, lengthy workdays, and stress, contributed to fatigue. A variety of treatments, such as urging drivers to get adequate sleep, setting driving time restrictions, and offering rest breaks, could be utilized to lower the risk of accidents caused by fatigue. These difficulties could endanger both the driver and the passengers, and they needed to be addressed in order to improve driving behavior. This mattered the most to the drivers who were willing to take actions ahead of their will for them to drive vehicles in a safe manner, without any possible conflict and with the accordance of the law, they would improve the rising cases of accidents due to reckless driving.

In spite of that, it is also vital to remember that drivers are also accountable for their emotions and actions and that the external factors are not solely the reasons why reckless driving happens. According to a journal article titled "Reckless Driving Law in the Philippines - What You Need to Know" published in 2023, it is driving without being cautious in controlling their vehicle. Such as using phones while driving, talking to other people in the middle of the road and being out of focus. Recent work in the fields suggests that the challenges faced by jeepney drivers may not always result in aggressive driving. Other criteria, such as personality or driving style, may play a larger influence when determining whether or not a driver is negligent as there are numerous factors that play to influence the driver's performance together with other circumstances that enable them to fully engage in the importance of driving and ensuring the passengers safety. Regardless of whether they drive a jeepney or other vehicles, they should be alert when driving to avoid any accidents. (Batara, 2021). Although reckless driving is punishable by law, there are still a lot of drivers who don't consider driving as serious as it takes when accidents happen. Driving without caution makes it dangerous as they don't consider other vehicles around them, especially the safety of their own and the passengers.

The Impact of Work Conditions on Jeepney Drivers' Performance and Urban Mobility

A substantial amount of existing study has explored the daily challenges faced by Jeepney drivers, providing valuable insights and knowledge about the Jeepney drivers. Encompassing their resilience, and hardship against the numerous difficulties and challenges they have frequently encountered at work (Tus, 2021). However, there has been insufficient research into the workspace of Jeepney drivers. Considering that Jeepneys are constructed from low quality materials, primarily designed for cost-effectiveness, rather than prioritizing the comfort and safety. For this reason, their workplace was typically cramped, with insufficient spaces in which they had to spend long hours sitting, subjecting them to uncomfortable positions and exposure to extreme weather conditions in the absence of adequate features (Rogelio et al., 2018). As a result, this lack of attention to their workplace conditions could potentially have led to more serious consequences on their physical health, which might affect their ability to provide effective public transportation services, leaving many aspects of this issue still remaining unclear.

Due to a variety of factors such as population growth, economic expansion, and the increased use of personal vehicles, traffic demand during peak hours has often exceeded the road's carrying capacity, worsening traffic problems and posing risks to public safety (Labalan, 2022). It was evident that Pasig City lacked sufficient public transit options, leading to the majority of residents relying on their own cars. While road widening was considered as a potential solution, it was recognized that it might take some time to address the issue effectively; therefore, a more favorable approach appeared to be the implementation of a multimodal transit system. The aim was to enhance urban mobility, ultimately reducing the dependence on personal vehicles and thereby mitigating the factors contributing to traffic congestion.

In contemplating the limited research on Jeepney drivers' workspaces, one must inquire how these work conditions truly affected their performance. As Borres (2019) underscored, the physical demands intrinsic to their tasks loomed large and could conceivably have stood as a pivotal factor in the myriad challenges confronting Jeepney drivers. This prompted us to ponder whether the adverse consequences of cramped spaces, low ceilings, damaged seats, and the absence of air-conditioning on their physical well-being extended to impairing their driving capabilities. Additionally, the assertion made by Meteier (2021) regarding the presence of more ergonomic workspaces in modern automobiles, encompassing not only primary driving duties but also auxiliary tasks, amplified the urgency of investigating whether inadequately designed workspaces in traditional Jeepneys acted as hindrances to drivers' overall performance. Given the apparent absence of standardized design and planning processes for Jeepney drivers, divergent from their counterparts in other vehicle types, one cannot help but question whether this resulted in suboptimal workstations and unfavorable driving conditions, potentially compromising their health and safety. Moreover, given the cost-effective nature of public Jeepney design, it begs the question of whether these cost-cutting measures detrimentally affected drivers' capacity to identify potential hazards.

In addition to what has already been discussed regarding the constant causes of traffic and unnoticed blockages on the roads of Pasig City, it remains unclear whether there will be a solution for reducing the massive traffic not just in Pasig City but also in other parts of the country. Several projects have been created and implemented by the government, but little to no progress has been observed. This includes the addition of government-supported buses and the implementation of coding/restrictions on PUJs to reduce the volume of vehicles on the streets. Furthermore, jeepney drivers of old jeepney models have not really benefited from all the solutions that the government has come up with. It is evident that the government has highly focused its attention on modernizing jeepney transportation in the Philippines (Atos, M. S. Q., et al., 2021).

Consequently, the various factors contributing to reckless driving among Jeepney drivers must be analyzed thoroughly, as the consequences of such behavior can result in property damage, traffic congestion, and pose risks to both passengers and drivers themselves (Philkotse, 2021). Jeepneys are often criticized for exacerbating heavy traffic and congestion, as they lack designated stops and tend to pick up and drop off passengers even in non-designated areas (Westerman, 2018). Therefore, additional studies are warranted to delve into the work-related challenges faced by Jeepney drivers and their connection to their driving behavior. Understanding the lived experiences of Jeepney drivers, including their cultural expressions, social interactions, and personal observations, can shed light on the myriad factors contributing to reckless driving. Such research can discern whether these behaviors stem from workplace challenges or aggressive driving tendencies, while also revealing the struggles and coping mechanisms influencing their driving habits. Consequently, a more detailed examination of these factors is essential for comprehending the interplay between the work struggles and navigational behavior of Jeepney drivers and how these factors impact accidents and traffic.

Therefore, through the analysis of these factors, researchers gained an understanding of the root causes behind traffic and congestion in Pasig City. This understanding has been immensely valuable for studying the challenges faced by Jeepney drivers and their navigation habits at work. It was crucial for stakeholders, including officials, transportation agencies, and the community, to grasp the underlying reasons behind reckless driving among Jeepney drivers in Pasig City. This study addressed a range of issues such as influences, government regulations, traffic congestion, and financial hardships, but it often overlooked the connection between their working conditions, travel patterns, and the specific difficulties they encountered. This study acknowledged the importance of shedding light on these aspects and comprehending the day-to-day lives of these drivers. Further research and studies were conducted to identify problems and best practices by comparing experiences of Jeepney drivers in Pasig City with those in urban areas in the Philippines or even other countries. Different regions implemented strategies to tackle this issue, prompting questions about which location, like Marikina City, devised effective measures for reducing traffic congestion. For instance, Marikina planned on constructing an integrated transport hub (Lim 2020). If the integrated transportation system proved effective, it would result in an increase in commuters and a decrease in traffic congestion. Implementing designated bike lanes and enforcing traffic laws rigorously were two of the measures undertaken by Marikina City.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative approach and a descriptive-narrative research design. This design is utilized to understand and explore the experiences and perspectives of the Jeepney Drivers' in their work environment, as well as to collect more detailed narratives from the participants, providing an in-depth exploration of the work struggles they experience (Sharma, 2019). Moreover, semi-structured one-on-one interviews are also used to collect the data from the participants, which promotes an open and flexible conversation about their thoughts and perspectives (Mashuri et al., 2022).

Participants

Purposive sampling approach was the method used by the researchers to meticulously select the study participants. Consequently, by using this method, the researchers were able to effectively gather in-depth knowledge and firsthand accounts from jeepney drivers. The study consisted of a total of seven (7) participants, which was in accordance with established qualitative research standards (Hennink & Kaiser, 2022). Related to this, the researchers purposely selected participants who were 28 years old and above, had at least 5 years of experience in driving conventional jeepneys, and were actively driving routes within Pasig City, Metro Manila. In order to guarantee that the data gathered appropriately reflects the target population and to offer a thorough grasp of the driving experience in Pasig City, this demographic selection was created.

Instrument

A semi-structured interview guide was employed to gather qualitative data from jeepney drivers in Pasig City, Metro Manila, Philippines. The interview guide encompassed a range of topics pertaining to the employment concerns and driving practices of jeepney drivers. The interviews commenced with inquiries into the driver's background, including their name, age, tenure as a jeepney driver, customary route, and average daily working hours. Subsequently, the interviewer delved into the driver's work-related challenges, such as traffic congestion, jeepney modernization initiatives, encountered difficulties, and strategies adopted to navigate unforeseen routes in San Joaquin, Pasig City. Prior to conducting the interviews, the questionnaire and methodology were meticulously evaluated by academic experts to ensure the research adhered to professional and ethical standards. By seeking expert validation of the questionnaires and methods, researchers can gain assurance of the reliability and significance of the data they collect. Upon validation of the questionnaires and methods, the researchers proceeded with the interviews.

Procedure

The researchers collected data in a systematic manner, following established procedures. The researchers began by explaining the study to the potential participants, in which they provided context for the chosen topic, highlighted its significance, and outlined the research objectives.

During the study, the researcher recruited seven (7) jeepney drivers with at least five years of experience who had experienced significant work-related issues. Participants signed a consent form prior to the interview, and a semi-structured interview guide was used to collect qualitative data on their job-related issues and navigational behaviors. To ensure comfort and freedom of expression, the interview lasted thirty minutes and was conducted in Tagalog.

After the interview, participants were assured that the gathered data would be kept confidential and would only be used for academic purposes. The responses of the participants were recorded and analyzed using appropriate techniques, and the results were presented and discussed in the study.

During analysis, researchers considered the richness of the narratives, identifying recurring themes and patterns that illuminate the drivers' challenges. The process also involved coding and categorizing the data to uncover insights into the socio-economic and environmental factors affecting their work.

Ethical Considerations

Before interviewing the individuals, the participants received informed consent that was clear, understandable, and clear with the research's purpose, potential risks, and benefits. The researchers also clearly defined the aim and objectives of the study, along with the research question. The researchers also protect and take precautions to prevent the identities of the participants from being used or known by others (Evergreen, 2023). The participants will not be exposed to any risks that could harm them physically or emotionally. The researchers upheld the study's ideals and objectives without pressuring any participant who had declined to participate or be interviewed. Thus, any participant is allowed to quit the interview whenever they want. The information gathered was handled properly, used ethically, and treated as confidential. Moreover, participants will be given transparent access to research results, and accuracy is ensured by preventing misinterpretations and exaggerations as well as responsible information use.

Results and Discussion

This entails detailed perspectives and information that was gathered using a semi-structured one-on-one interview with the participants. The research findings present the daily challenges that the Jeepney Drivers' experience, challenges, and various factors affecting their navigational behaviors.

Table 1. *Emerging Themes*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
Perception and Experiences of Jeepney Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic Struggles in the Jeepney Profession - Interactions Between Drivers and Passengers - Work Struggles Experienced on the Road
Key Factors that Influenced the Decision Making of Jeepney Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impacts of Road Conditions to Jeepney Drivers - Jeepney driver's interaction with the community and its effect on the socio-cultural aspect. - Driver and Commuters Safety on Road.
Jeepney Driver's Act in Accordance with the Intervention Regarding Transportation Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impact of Intervention to their Livelihood and the Financial consequences. - Labored Experiences of Jeepney Driver's in Working Setting - Effect of Strategies and the Way They Adapt to the Possible Difficulties

The theme Perception and Experiences of Jeepney Drivers, shows the numerous factors that contribute to the daily lives of the Jeepney Drivers. It includes their perspectives, work struggles, and experiences while on the road. The first subordinate theme showed that Jeepney drivers have a significant problem with the economic changes, including the rising prices of fuel and food and unpredictable income, as their income only comes from how many commuters ride their Jeepneys. Due to this, the participants stated the difficulty in maintaining their vehicles due to high maintenance costs and the little income they receive from driving Jeepneys. thus, contributing to their financial strain. In addition, in the second subordinate theme, the participants shared their interaction experiences with the passengers and other drivers. The result revealed that some passengers were understanding and kind; the other passengers were perceived as demanding and occasionally rude. However, many of the Jeepney drivers endure this and instead are patient with these kinds of passengers. Moreover, the third subordinate theme indicated that participants also have struggles they experience on the roads while driving. The findings indicated that constant traffic, road construction, and congestion affect many aspects of their work, particularly their income and daily quotas.

Then, the theme, Key Factors that Influenced the Decision Making of Jeepney Drivers serves as an entire focus that explores the various factors that influenced the decision and navigational behavior of the Jeepney drivers. While the first subordinate themes revealed that road conditions while driving their vehicle have a high influence on their driving decisions, while navigating the roads, the participants asserted that many of the drivers need to adapt and change their driving strategies in response to congested streets, particularly the cramped and uneven roads. In relation to this, the second subordinate theme entailed the jeepney drivers' interaction with their community, specifically the passengers. Therefore, it allows the participants to learn and respond to the preferences of their passengers.

Furthermore, the third subordinate theme showed that safety for both the driver and the passengers is also integral whenever they maneuver their jeepneys. Thus, participants adhere to many regulations to promote a safe way of driving. This also includes following traffic regulations, maintaining a good condition of their Jeepney, and different protocols that ensure that there will be no accidents or any risk for everyone.

Finally, the theme, Jeepney Driver's Act in Accordance with the Intervention Regarding Transportation Policy, revealed several aspects of how a Jeepney Driver adapts and responds to the changes due to transportation policy. Moreover, as for the first subordinate theme, the participants imply that intervention policies affect the economic sustainability of Jeepney drivers due to policy changes, thus, affecting their income as well. In addition to this, the second subordinate theme delves into the experiences of the Jeepney drivers in their work setting. The result finds that the daily challenges of driving cause physical and emotional exhaustion for the participants due to the challenges in their work environment. Moreover, the third subordinate theme explores the resilience and patience of the jeepney drivers despite the numerous challenges and difficulties they experience. For this reason, many participants stated that they employed different strategies to cope with and adapt to these difficulties, which shows the drivers' ability to navigate through the challenges and find a safe solution.

The theme, Perception and Experiences of Jeepney Drivers' discusses the different struggles that jeepney drivers experience every day on the road, from stubborn passengers to economic problems. The results revealed that each participant that was interviewed shared common problems and showed how they affected their everyday life just like how a participant expresses his dismay, "yung traffic mauubos yung oras mo e. imbis na makaikot ka ng lima, apat nalang". Another one stated: "Syempre bawas na kita e, kase unti lang ikot nyan, apat edi bawas na kita nyan." They both stated how traffic problems affect their income because whenever they're stuck in traffic, their time is being wasted and it greatly affects their rotation, which would also mean that their income would not be enough. In addition, a participant explained what he usually does: "Control control nalang, control nalang sa sarili kasi pag nararamdaman mong ganun tapos mag paapekto ka ay highbloodrin ka lang at atakihin ka." whenever he's on the road and traffic becomes a hindrance to his livelihood. Karmela et al. (2022) concur that driving a vehicle is an intricate thing that can involve major differences in mental workload. Drivers must process a large amount of information coming from outside the car, such as traffic intensity, traffic signs, and so on. Their study found that frustration level and mental demand are some of the contributing factors to jeepney drivers' mental workload. It is important for jeepney drivers to have self-control because, according to Borres & Javier (2019), as fatigue and mental workload accumulate, passenger safety diminishes. Both studies corroborate this study, as it shows how jeepney drivers' daily experiences contribute to their navigational behavior.

Meanwhile, the other theme, Key Factors that Influenced the Decision Making of Jeepney Drivers, discusses broad influences on jeepney drivers' decision-making processes, with the goal of identifying the key factors that significantly influence their choices while navigating the streets. The findings indicated that every participant experienced comparable problems and provided evidence of how those problems impacted their daily lives. In the same way that a participant expresses his dismay, "Para sakin kaya ito yung pinili kong ruta kasi medyo malapit lang yung bahay namin tapos wala pang gaanong huli at ang pinaka huli lang namin eh yung mag iba kami ng daan," They knew that their proximity to home influences their decisions. Conversely, a participant said, "Obligasyon ng driver yun na ingatan yung pasahero." That shows that they attempt to avoid taking detours and prioritize the safety of their passengers and proximity to home. Atos et al., (2023) emphasized the need for drivers to modify their routes in order to travel on congested roads more efficiently. These findings make clear how crucial road conditions are to the decision-making process of jeepney drivers. These results highlight the significance of road conditions in the decision-making process of jeepney drivers. The opinions of participants aid in determining the factors influencing the choices made by jeepney drivers. Consistent with previous studies, the relevance of adaptive driving and route selection techniques that consider participant preferences and environmental factors is underscored by their consideration of home distance and road conditions.

Lastly, the theme, Jeepney Driver's Act in Accordance with the Intervention Regarding Transportation Policy, tackles how jeepney drivers acclimate to the policies and interventions made by the government and how they affect them positively and negatively. The results exposed the different attitudes of jeepney drivers toward the interventions made by the government. Some are just fine with it, while others are not. Just like how a participant stated his answer to the existing policies, "parang wala akong nararamdaman sa polisiya, yung polisiya para ano lang pabalik balik nalang yung aayusin nila tapos ilang araw babalik na naman," it seems like it has no effect on the development of jeepney drivers' concerns like traffic, inadequate income, and road problems. In contrast, there was a participant who cited more positively: "So sa rules and regulations dito sa pasig kung susunod ka rin naman wala naman magiging problema gaya nung para makaiwas din sa traffic kunwari syempre maiiwasan yung obstruction mabilis yung daloy ng ano traffic kaya napapadali." Moreover, another participant shared how other jeepney drivers act: "Dumidiskarte nalang kami, kanya kanyang diskarte nalang mga driver. Kung saan makakalusot mga driver, lusot-lusot nalang," that show how resilient they are with the policies and interventions that the government has made. One of the major interventions made by the government was to make modern jeepneys to lessen pollution and increase commuters' safety. According to Cantero (2019), jeepney drivers see the Jeepney Modernization Program as a way to address jeepney-related issues. Despite appreciating the program's goals, they oppose modernization due to budgetary constraints, citing high expenditures that are too expensive for most drivers and are likely to create additional charges. Drivers choose to continue with the familiar jeepney structure, preferring repair and upkeep rather than completely altering public utility jeepneys. Despite these worries, jeepney drivers express hope for the government's assistance throughout the Jeepney Modernization Program's

implementation.

Conclusions

The current study sought to investigate and comprehend one of the most crucial features of jeepney drivers' work challenges and navigational behavior. Several observations were gathered addressing the experiences, obstacles, and coping techniques brought by modern jeepneys. The Jeepney drivers' travels are complicated because they have been coping with economic issues that have solely impacted their driving and livelihood style while working, but, despite the dangers of the road, they adhere to the government's policies and standards. They continue to pursue it for the sake of themselves and their loved ones. Most jeepney drivers must be physically fit in order to meet road, work, and navigational problems in front of commuters and other jeepney drivers. They should constantly be presentable and understanding, especially during times of testing. Their earnings are insufficient owing to rising oil prices, but they can't do anything if there are fewer passengers and more like them; most of them are fathers who suffer every time they don't give and provide for their families. In addition to traffic and road policies, the key point is that they follow the traffic laws, and the government refuses to assist them.

The researchers recommend the study to the government and transportation departments, as it allows jeepney drivers to speak up and have their concerns heard. Moreover, the researchers also recommend the study to commuters so they can gain a better understanding of the work struggles and navigational behaviors of jeepney drivers, which also affect passengers. In addition, this study is also suggested for future researchers; this research will benefit as it will serve as a reference for further development of the study and the discovery of new, similar findings. This study reveals the working struggles and various factors that contribute to the navigational behavior of Jeepney drivers and affect their daily lives. Hence, to address these issues and promote a good working condition, the researchers suggest that first, collaboration and consideration of the commuters are needed to build a better relationship between the commuter and a driver, from which both of them would benefit. Second, there must be programs that attempt to provide financial aid and/or social welfare benefits to drivers due to their unpredictable income, which contributes to the numerous working challenges that they confront on a daily basis.

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